

**FINITE ELEMENT AIDED DESIGN
OF LAMINATED AND SANDWICH PLATES
USING REANALYSIS METHODS**

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ABSTRACT

Classical finite element programs are not well suited to the design of composite structures, because they are primarily analysis tools and need much time for the input and treatment of the data and also for the interpretation of the results. The aim of the present work is to develop a program which allows very fast analyses and reanalyses for design process, using a fast reanalysis method with changes of data and conditions. Speed in the analysis is obtained by :

- simplification of the analysed structure and limitations in its geometrical generality,
- improvements in numerical methods.

The use of the program is made easy with interactive user-friendly facilities.

Keywords : Design, Finite Elements, Numerical methods, Reanalysis, Composite structures, Laminated Plates, Sandwich Plates.

1. INTRODUCTION

The finite element method is presently a basic tool for the analysis process of structures. However, it may require a long and complex process, even for classical structures.

For composite structures, the difficulties of finding pertinent and simple models for the material behaviour makes finite element analyses ever more difficult. A review of existing programs for the design of composite structures (general or special purpose programs) shows that generally they are only analysis tools with no design facilities, which highly increase the design cost, due to three important penalties :

- heavy input data (specially for the material properties),
- long computational time (specially through the use of specific finite elements adapted to more complex behaviour of composite structures),
- excessive time spent for the output process (related to multilayer structures).

Application of the finite element method to design is of course even more time-consuming and difficult. Design requires treatment of multiple cases for the same structure with variations.

Inclusion of a finite element program in an optimization process is frequently proposed as a way for design. In our opinion, this is generally impracticable. A more realistic approach is the reanalysis methods, which have received some attention for several years. As stated by Kane et al. ¹, *the term reanalysis denotes any technique that allows for the subsequent analysis of a modified problem with less expenditure of computational resources than required to compute the response of the original problem is reused in the analysis of the modified problem.*

We have investigated the use of reanalysis methods for the design of composites structures, specially to avoid the aforementioned drawback. From our experience, changes for design process can be graded in order of increasing difficulties as :

- applied forces,
- boundary conditions,
- material properties,
- geometry.

The present development illustrates the reanalysis methods for the first and second types.

2. PRESENT REANALYSIS METHOD

The reanalysis method proposed by Verchery ² permits a fast reanalysis for changes in kinematic constraints and applied forces as well, and gives an important gain in computation time. The kinematic constraints mean here boundary conditions, symmetries conditions, inextensibility or incompressibility constraints. This method is based on the fact that the rigid body motions cause the singularities of the classical equilibrium system of discrete elastic structures :

$$\mathbf{K} \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{f} \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{K} is the structural stiffness matrix, \mathbf{u} the displacement vector and \mathbf{f} the total force vector. In the traditional analysis method, this equation can be solved only by introducing the boundary conditions. Further, when the boundary conditions are changed, the whole process has to be started again from the beginning, solving frequently a very large linear system. This process is very time consuming. An other advantage of this reanalysis method is that it can be applied to local changes in material and geometrical properties (Huang et al. ³).

The resolution for the reanalysis process is decomposed in two steps. A first step is the computation of the flexibility matrix \mathbf{S} , which is a quasi-inverse of the stiffness matrix :

$$\mathbf{S} \mathbf{K} = \mathbf{K} \mathbf{S} = \mathbf{I} - \mathbf{R} \mathbf{R}^T . \quad (2)$$

This flexibility matrix is obtained through a regularization process, described theoretically by Verchery ¹ and numerically by Loredo ⁴. Here \mathbf{R} is the $n \times r$ matrix, the columns of which are the eigenvectors, chosen to be orthonormal, for the zero eigenvalues of the stiffness and flexibility matrices \mathbf{K} and \mathbf{S} .

While this first step is general, the second step introduces all the data relevant to the kinematic constraints and loading conditions. The kinematic constraints (including the boundary conditions) are supposed to be independent and linear :

$$\mathbf{L}^T \mathbf{u} = \delta , \quad (3)$$

in which \mathbf{L} is a $p \times n$ matrix with rank p , and δ are p prescribed values. These kinematic constraints develop reactive forces \mathbf{f}_r expressible in terms of p reaction parameters ϕ :

$$\mathbf{f}_r = - \mathbf{L} \phi . \quad (4)$$

The total forces \mathbf{f} are the sum of these reaction forces and the given forces \mathbf{f}_d . The solution for the displacement \mathbf{u} can be expressed in the full form :

$$\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{S} (\mathbf{f}_d - \mathbf{L} \phi) + \mathbf{R} \omega. \quad (5)$$

The rigid body motions ω and reaction parameters ϕ are obtained for a discriminant system :

$$\begin{bmatrix} -\mathbf{L}^T \mathbf{S} \mathbf{L} & \mathbf{L}^T \mathbf{R} \\ \mathbf{R}^T \mathbf{L} & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \phi \\ \omega \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \delta - \mathbf{L}^T \mathbf{S} \mathbf{f}_d \\ \mathbf{R}^T \mathbf{f}_d \end{Bmatrix}. \quad (6)$$

The order $p+r$ of this discriminant system is much less than the original system (Equation 1), especially for problems with large degrees of freedom and small number of constraints. With this method, the reanalysis under various boundary conditions is made easier. This can be applied to aided design, which requires fast reanalysis processes for full efficiency. It can simplify the solutions for contact problems and elastic crack propagation problems, which otherwise need long iteration methods, and can be useful for sub-structuring of large or repetitive structures.

3. GENERAL DESCRIPTION OF FEAD-LASP PROGRAM

To evaluate our very efficient and general reanalysis methods, which are not based on multiple automatic optimisations used in any universal finite element program but entirely piloted by the user, we developed specific finite element program, called FEAD-LASP (Finite Element Aided Design of Laminated And Sandwich Plates). Developed for the design of laminated and sandwich plates, this program was planned for and adapted to them. It permits both analysis and design of laminated and sandwich plates in linear elasticity. Our principal goals were :

- good compromise between the computation time and the treatment capacities of the program,
- significant decrease of the computation time in order to reduce the waiting time of the users,
- fully interactive package, in the sense to be self-explanatory and user-friendly.

To reach the above aims, we choose a particular set of data and methods as presented in the following.

Simple geometries and pre-defined meshes were considered, i.e. rectangular composite and sandwich panels (in bending and in-plane deformations) with pre-defined regular meshes, which nevertheless cover a wide field of practical needs.

We selected a generalized stress-strain law, which describes efficiently the behaviour of both laminated plates with shear effects and sandwich plates. It takes into account all the specific features of these structures, including bending, in-plane, bending-membrane coupling with transverse shear stiffnesses (based on the extended laminated plate theory) ; as we proceed with global stiffnesses, the definition problem of the stacking sequence may be treated separately (Verchery⁵).

Using the normalized stiffnesses (Tsai et al. ⁶), the generalized stress-strain law is written :

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N \\ M \\ Q \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} h A^* & \frac{h^2}{2} B^* & 0 \\ \frac{h^2}{2} B^* & \frac{h^3}{12} D^* & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & h G^* \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon^0 \\ \kappa \\ \gamma \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (7)$$

where N , M and Q are the in-plane forces, bending moments and shear forces ; ϵ^0 , κ and γ are the membrane strains, curvatures and shearing strains ; A^* , B^* , D^* and G^* are the normalized in-plane, coupling, bending and shear stiffness.

Various particular methods are used to decrease the computation time. In particular, a faster method for the computation and assembly of the stiffness matrices of the elements was derived and tested. It reduces the corresponding time very significantly, using pre-computation and compact storage (only non-zero terms) of dimensionless parts of the global stiffness matrix elements. The reanalysis

method previously presented is incorporated in the program to make the design process faster again and allow changes in both boundary conditions and loading.

In view of the features nowadays provided by system environment such as Macintosh or Microsoft Windows, we developed an interface adapted to our research field, presenting similar facilities. This interactive user-friendly package, i.e. self-explanatory process through the use of total interactivity and pop-up menus technique for the data input and results manipulation, was developed for users who have little or no knowledge of the internal structure and methods of the program. Figure 1 illustrates one of the window mouse pull-down menus used for data input.

4. IMPLEMENTATION OF FEAD-LASP PROGRAMS

A 16-node thick plate finite element (Figure 2) was retained. It is based on a kinematic and material similarity between laminated and sandwich structures and the three dimensional finite element with two nodes in the thickness and a fictitious equivalent material with properties varying along the thickness (El Shaikh ⁷). This process applied to the finite element method allows to use the classical finite elements in a slightly modified form and avoids resorting to special finite elements.

During the program development, a dimensional analysis, using the fact that a regular mesh was used, showed that only about 10% of the global matrix coefficients in a non-dimensional form can generate the global matrix. Consequently, these quantities were computed and stored as data in the program. These data are common to all types of plates, so the assembly process is reduced to the multiplication of different data blocks by dimensional and materials properties. The analysis computational time (assembly process and solving) was compared with a classical finite element program. This comparison showed the high efficiency of FEAD-LASP program compared with the method used in the classical finite element program.

The first version (FEAD-LASP 1.0) presented at ICCM-7 (Ghazal et al. ⁸) was developed in FORTRAN 77. Changes in applied forces, using the classical and simple reanalysis process to resolve Equation 1, was implemented (Ghazal et al. ⁸, Aivazzadeh et al. ⁹). Its principle is to solve simultaneously the loading cases from the beginning. These cases correspond to concentrated normal unit force at each node on a face of the plate. f is no more a vector but a matrix. Any practical loading can then be described as a linear combination of these basic cases. For each loading, the data input process provides the load coefficients and the solution is obtained by the same linear combination of the basic solutions. This combination is almost instantaneous and the process can be reapplied by the designer as many times as required. The reanalysis for change in boundary conditions was performed (as in classical finite element programs) by coming back to the global stiffness matrix, then starting again the time-consuming solution.

In FEAD-LASP 2.0, the new reanalysis method developed by Verchery ² was introduced in order to allow both changes in the displacement boundary conditions and loads without coming back to the initial system (Equation 1). The structure of FEAD-LASP 2.0 is schematised in Figure 3, in which kinematic constraints are limited to boundary conditions. The program is written in C language to better manage the computer system facilities.

A study was made, concerning the comparison of times of different steps by running FEAD-LASP 1.0 on various platforms. Several micro-computers and work-stations were used to test the numerical part : it was found that personal computers as well as low cost work-stations were well suited for a fast numerical treatment, i.e. only a few minutes for the first analysis, and reanalysis in seconds. Moreover, it was seen that, even in the case of very low-cost micro-computers, the total time was reasonable in a design process. To run the program satisfactorily, it is necessary to have a graphic display and an arithmetic coprocessor. The minimal required configuration for storage capacity is about 20-Mbyte hard disc drive and 2-Mbyte RAM memory. However, a 40-Mbyte hard disc drive is recommended.

5. CONCLUSION

This paper has given a general description of FEAD-LASP program. The link of pre- and post-processors (data input and output processing) with the analysis stage (finite elements) to form a

design process was described and the attractive features for the user, obtained by significant reductions in computation time and user-friendly package, were emphasized.

Improvements of this program are in progress. A data base of efficient material properties description (Kandil et al. ¹⁰), numerical optimisation techniques in the reanalysis method (Loredo ⁴) and possibilities of material changes (Huang et al. ³) will be incorporated.

The simplicity and the generality of the explicit reanalysis method incorporated in FEAD-LASP 2.0 allow to anticipate a modular development of the program or the creation of new softwares, tacking into account the geometrical variety of structures or the use of other finite elements.

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Figure 1 : Principal pull-down menu for data input.

Figure 2 - The 16-node thick plate finite element used in FEAD-LASP.

Figure 3 - General description of FEAD-LASP program